

DIMENSIONAL STABILITY OF CFRP MIRRORS FOR SPACE TELESCOPES UNDER LOW TEMPERATURE ENVIRONMENT

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1 Introduction

CFRP (carbon fiber reinforced plastics) has physical properties superior to other candidate materials for main mirrors of space telescopes. Nonetheless, practical use of CFRP mirrors have not yet been achieved except developing models [1]. The primary reason is considered that surface accuracy of CFRP mirrors has not satisfied severe requirements for visible or near-infrared light space telescopes. Those applications require surface accuracy of nm level. The second reason is performance reliability and assurance in orbit, which is usually a hard barrier that any new materials must break through. The following issues have to be resolved;

1. to attain the required spherical preciseness and surface roughness
2. to demonstrate dimensional stability against space environment
3. to verify long term dimensional stability in orbit

We achieved spherical preciseness of 0.1 μ m RMS (root mean square) and surface roughness of 10 nm RMS and showed spherical shape stability of 10 nm RMS against moisture absorption [2]. Mechanisms which affect long term dimensional stability have been studied and discussed in terms of physical aging and creep behaviour [3].

In this study, dimensional stability of CFRP mirrors under cryogenic environment was observed using a laser interferometer. Infrared telescopes are often operated under cryogenic temperature in order to reduce thermal noise. CFRP is able to be designed to have nearly zero CTE at specified temperature, and have relatively small thermal shrinkage from room to cryogenic temperature [4]. That is preferable feature for keeping surface accuracy. However, behaviour of CFRP mirrors and

dimensional stability of their surface preciseness at low or cryogenic temperatures has not been reported.

2 Samples and test procedure

Mirror samples used in the experiment were composed of all CFRP sandwich panels with CFRP face skins and CFRP flex core [2]. High modulus pitch carbon fiber of K1352U (Mitsubishi Plastics) and low moisture expansion resin of cyanate ester EX1515 (TenCate) as matrix were used for face skins. Stack of the face skins was quasi-isotropic [0/ \pm 45/90]_{4s} of 16 plies. Thickness was 2.0 mm. The core was manufactured using high modulus pitch carbon fiber YSH-50A (Nippon Graphite Fiber)/Cyanate RS-3 (TenCate) cloth prepreg monosheet. Fiber direction was 45° to thickness direction. The core size was 3/8", core thickness, 10 mm and core shape, flex. Diameter of the mirrors was 150 mm, thickness, 24 mm and concave surface curvature, 454 mm. The mirror surface was coated with epoxy resin by a replica technique in order to improve surface roughness [5]. Replicated surface was buffed and then vacuum-deposited with aluminum as reflect layer. Coefficient of thermal expansion of flat sandwich panel of the same composition was 1.0 x 10⁻⁷ /K at room temperature.

Fig. 1 Experimental apparatus

Surface profile of the mirrors was measured using a laser interferometer (Zygo). The mirror was set in a vacuum chamber with cooling shroud and laser of spherical wave was irradiated to the mirror surface through quartz window of the chamber from the laser interferometer (Fig.1). An observed typical interference pattern was shown in Fig.2. Large number of interference stripes indicated that the mirror used was rough in surface accuracy initially.

Fig.2 Observed interference pattern

The chamber was evacuated up to 1×10^{-4} Pa and the mirror was cooled down from room temperature to liquid nitrogen temperature. Surface profile of the mirror was measured at every 30 K in both cooling-down and heating-up process. Surface preciseness was estimated as deviation from an ideal spherical surface. Radius of curvature could not be determined in this apparatus. Before and after cooling, surface roughness was measured using a 3D optical surface profiler (Zygo). Moving from the original surface was calculated by extraction of the reference surface pixel by pixel from measured data. The reference surface was defined under condition of room temperature and atmosphere before cooling started. Surface roughness was calculated using He-Ne laser wavelength 633nm.

3 Results and discussion

Fig.3 shows 3-dimensional surface profiles of the CFRP mirror in different temperatures. Profiles were deviation from an ideal spherical surface, where piston, tilt and power were calibrated. The replicated mirror before cooled as shown in the top of Fig.3 (a) had a smooth surface of 10 nm RMS (root mean square) in roughness and surface asperities such as fiber print-through [5] were not observed. Surface accuracy of the original condition was 8.8λ , $5.6 \mu\text{m}$ in PV (peak to valley) and 1.1λ , $0.70\mu\text{m}$ in RMS.

The center was concave from ideal spherical surface and the edge was concave and convex like a saddle shape. Red arrow indicates fiber direction of the outermost layer of stacked unidirectional prepregs.

At a glance of Fig.3, the overall mirror shape did not seem to change till 210K. At lower temperatures than 180K, the center concavity and edge convexoconcave became shallower than the reference. Surface preciseness at 80K was 5.1λ , $3.2 \mu\text{m}$ PV and 0.77λ , $0.49\mu\text{m}$ RMS. This change of shape remained till 240K in heating-up process and diminished at 270K. At room temperature, the shape returned to the original, though concavity and convexity of edge looked to change position and height. Left upper side of the mirror became high and area beyond measurable level widened.

Fig.3 Surface profiles in cooling

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Many straight and parallel lines were clearly shown in Fig.3 (c) 270K and 300K in direction indicated by blue arrow. The direction was perpendicular to fiber orientation in the utmost layer. Straight lines were also observed in direction parallel to the fiber.

Fig.4 and Fig.5 shows moving of surface preciseness PV and RMS as figures respectively in cooling and heating processes. Both PV and RMS became smaller as temperature lowered. That means that the mirror shape happened to change to close to an ideal spherical shape. Values of PV and RMS were smaller in heating than cooling process, and returned to the start at room temperature. Green dots in Fig.4 and Fig.5 showed surface preciseness in atmosphere. The surface preciseness after cooled was 9.5λ , $6.0\mu\text{m}$ PV and 1.0λ , $0.63\mu\text{m}$ RMS. The surface preciseness differed by evacuation slightly.

Fig.4 Moving of surface preciseness PV at low temperatures

Fig.5 Moving of surface preciseness RMS at low temperatures

Difference of surface preciseness RMS from the reference was also shown as lower two lines in Fig.5. The difference became gradually large with lowering temperature. This inclination was converse to the surface preciseness PV or RMS. The difference was 2 times larger in heating than cooling process. After heated back to room temperature, the difference remained 4.9λ , $3.1\mu\text{m}$ PV and 0.40λ , $0.26\mu\text{m}$ RMS. On the other hand, surface preciseness PV or RMS was almost same to the reference.

Fig.6 shows difference from the reference in central area of $\phi 50\text{ mm}$ in the mirror. Both PV and RMS became larger as temperature lowered. Although values were smaller than in Fig.4 and Fig.5, inclination of PV change was contrary. RMS change was equivalent in cooling and heating process. The remained difference at room temperature in atmosphere after cooling was $0.43\mu\text{m}$ PV and $0.057\mu\text{m}$ RMS. Especially RMS was 4 times smaller than whole area. That was considered that there were at least two different types of mirror deformation, overall deformation such as twisting or warping and asperity of short pitch. Results in the whole mirror in Fig.4 and 5 were affected more strongly by overall warping deformation than the center.

Fig. 6 Difference from the original shape in central area of $\phi 50\text{mm}$ of the mirror

Fig.7 shows 3-d surface profile of difference from the reference. At 144K, there observed asperity patterns of around 10 to 15 mm pitch in

whole area. This scale was close to core size and resembled midscale ripples which observed on as-molded mirrors without replicating [5]. Large number of straight parallel lines was observed at 299K after cooled to 80K, and core-size pattern disappeared. The line pattern was another irreversible deformation remained on mirror surface other than overall warping.

Fig.7 Difference of surface preciseness

Fig. 8 Surface profile of area including line pattern

Fig.8 was a 3-d surface profile of 12.5 x12.5 mm area including line pattern. The direction of lines was parallel and perpendicular to fiber orientation of the utmost layer. Width of lines was 1 to 2 mm, and height was 0.1 to 0.15 μm .

Space between lines was 5 to several tens mm. $\pm 45^\circ$ pattern, which was fiber direction of the second and third layers, was not observed. However, this deformation was thought due to fiber tow as well as in [5].

4 Summary

Change of surface preciseness of all CFRP mirrors under cryogenic temperature was studied. Overall shape of the mirror remained stable to 210K. Under 210K, surface deformed, and there existed three patterns of deformation.

- 1) Overall warping or twisting
- 2) Line pattern
- 3) Core pattern

Overall warping and line pattern remained as irreversible deformation at room temperature after cooling and heating cycle. Surface preciseness of 9 μm PV and 0.70 μm RMS was not degraded yet. Difference was 0.4 μm PV and 0.06 μm RMS in the central area. Line pattern was parallel and perpendicular to fiber orientation of the utmost layer. Core size pattern which observed under 210K was diminished over 270K. Mechanism of deformation of surface profile of CFRP mirrors must be investigated to further detail for practical use.

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